

Effect Of Domain Size on 2d and 3d CFD Modeling of a Vertical Axis Wind Turbine

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Abstract Due to the rising pollution in the atmosphere and depleting fossil fuel supplies renewable sources of energy have started to gain popularity in the past few years. The vertical axis wind turbine (VAWT) has some distinct advantages over the conventional horizontal axis wind turbine (HAWT) which include no requirement of yaw control, ease of maintenance, etc., as a result the inclination of the industry towards vertical axis wind turbine (VAWT) is increased in the recent past. The performance of VAWT and its efficiency are investigated in this article using computational fluid dynamics simulation in ANSYS Fluent software. The current study simulates 2D and 3D three-bladed VAWT by using unsteady Reynolds-averaged Navier-Stokes (URANS) model. The current study systematically examines the effect of different domain sizes on the VAWT performance (i.e., minimize the effect of blockage and unreliability of the boundary condition) by keeping the blade profile, rotor diameter, chord length and setting angle fixed for the three-bladed VAWT operating at a modest tip speed ratio. The results obtained are validated with the available literature and later the domain size is varied for understanding its effect. It is concluded that the domain size has a significant impact on the numerical results and it is highly essential to opt efficient domain size for obtaining the correct behavior of wind flow pattern.

Keywords CFD, ANSYS Fluent, URANS, k- ϵ Turbulence Model, VAWT.

Introduction

Fossil fuels being the most popular option for the satisfying energy demand of current generations comes with the challenge of climate change. Wind energy, being the most promising renewable energy source, is crucial in addressing the fossil fuel crisis^[1]. Although it can lessen reliance on conventional resources as the primary energy source, several significant disadvantages restrict its viability in the current scenario. There is no denying that a thermal power plant has a higher power capacity than a wind turbine. Also, they are not always present due to seasonal variations in the weather. Although it can lessen reliance on conventional resources as the primary energy source, several significant disadvantages restrict its viability in the current scenario. There is no denying that a thermal power plant has a higher power capacity than a wind turbine. Also, they are not always present due to seasonal variations in the weather^[2]. The installation position of the primary shaft concerning the ground determines the classification of wind turbines into two categories: horizontal axis wind turbines (HAWTs) and vertical axis wind turbines (VAWTs)^[3]. Growing interest has been shown recently in vertical-axis wind turbines (VAWTs) for wind energy which is attributed to their omnidirectional capability, minimal installation and maintenance costs, scalability, and dependability^[4]. The Darrieus type vertical axis wind turbines (VAWTs) is a lift-based turbine that uses blades with cross sections shaped like airfoils have a simpler structure than HAWTs since they don't require a yaw control mechanism to operate in any direction of flow. Typically, VAWTs feature straight blades because they are simpler to produce than HAWTs' twisted blades. Furthermore, the ground placement of the generator and gearbox is made feasible by the design of VAWTs, which can simplify installation and maintenance. When compared to HAWTs, all of the features in VAWTs can lower their cost^[5].

Literature Review

Duty, D. et al. (2013): This paper presents a two-dimensional (2D) computational fluid dynamics (CFD) analysis of a vertical axis wind turbine (VAWT). The purpose of the study is to use CFD simulation to look into the VAWT's performance and flow characteristics. The simulation provides an understanding of the velocity and pressure distribution surrounding the turbine, as well as the power coefficient and overall efficiency of the turbine, by modelling the turbine shape, the boundary condition involved, the meshing and solver settings. As a crucial step in guaranteeing the validity and dependability of the simulation results, this study also assesses the experimental result's validation and compares it with the published journal^[6]. Zhang, L. et al. (2013): The main goal of this work was to improve the aerodynamic performance prediction of VAWT by examining the implications of the computational domain. As prior to meshing, the computational domain must be established, which is crucial for accuracy. When the computing domain is substantially smaller, there are fewer grids at a given grid density and time is saved. However, if the domain is too tiny, accuracy will suffer greatly. Because the flow velocity through the VAWT hasn't completely returned to the inflow speed, the wake flow pressure is significantly lower than the outlet pressure, which causes an adverse pressure gradient and recirculation at the outlet. Moreover, the recirculation zone widens as the adverse pressure gradient increases, producing computed results that have no relevance. Large computing domains, however, will result in longer computation times^[1]. Tjiu, W. et al. (2014): The central focus is to evaluate the configurations of Darrieus vertical axis

wind turbines (VAWTs), highlighting the shortcomings of each variation that impeded the evolution into large-scale rotor technology. An extensive chronology is provided as a pedigree diagram. The performance, components, and operational reliability of the variations are evaluated. Furthermore, the existing state and potential directions of Darrieus VAWT are discussed [9]. Rezaeiha, A. et al. (2017): The main purpose of the current study is to predict the performance of a vertical-axis wind turbine (VAWT) using 2-dimensional simulations with the unsteady Reynolds-averaged Navier-Stokes (URANS) and a domain size large enough to minimize the effects of blockage and uncertainties in the boundary conditions using computational fluid dynamics (CFD) simulation [4]. Celik, Y. et al. (2020): The main motivation for this work is to create a CFD start-up model in order to assess the self-starting behaviour of the H-type vertical axis wind turbines (VAWTs). In order to ensure the conservation of mass and momentum throughout the simulation, the computing domain is divided between a rotational domain, which houses the rotor, and a fixed rectangular outer domain. In order to guarantee the establishment of continuity in the flow field, interface boundary conditions are used to link the two regions. The blade surfaces are regarded as no-slip limits, and a zero-gauge pressure outlet is placed on the right side of the computational domain [7]. Soltanzadeh, B., M. et al. (2021): The main objective of this study is the construction and testing, under practical circumstances, of a straight-bladed VAWT with a high solidity ratio. Additionally, to investigate the impact of the pitch angle on the turbine's aerodynamic properties, numerical simulations were run to assess the turbine's aerodynamic performance at two pitch angles, 0 and 5 [8].

Methodology

Brief Description of VAWT Model

Blade type	NACA0015
Blade height	3m (for 3D)
Diameter of Rotor (D)	2.5m
Chord length	0.40 (40% of NACA0015 Original)
No. of Turbine blades	3
Wind speed	10m/s (Constant)
Tips speed	20 rad/s

NACA0015 Airfoil coordinates are taken from <http://airfoiltools.com> [2] shown in Fig.1 which is initially taken as open at trailing edge, later trailing edge closed in modelling tool.

Reynolds numbers (Re) for this research is 2×10^6 (approximately) which is calculated by

$$Re = \frac{\rho V D}{\mu}$$

Where ρ , V , D and μ are the density of air, Velocity, Diameter and dynamic viscosity respectively.

Boundary Conditions

For 2D Analysis:

Left boundary: Velocity inlet (10m/s Constant)

Top and bottom boundary: Specified shear (Zero slip)

Right boundary: Pressure Outlet

Turbine blades: No slip

Shaft: No slip

For 3D Analysis:

Left boundary: Velocity inlet (10m/s Constant)
 Top, bottom and sides boundary: Specified shear (Zero slip)
 Right boundary: Pressure Outlet
 Turbine blades: No slip

The entire computational zone is divided into three parts namely external (stationary), internal (stationary) and middle (rotating) which contains airfoils. The sliding mesh can be built by setting angular velocity of the rotating domain. The interface between each zone is set as the interface condition.

The airfoil surface has a boundary layer mesh installed in order to guarantee the accuracy of the complex flow computation near the wall. The following formula is used to calculate the first layer's thickness:

$$\Delta y = \frac{\mu y^+}{(\rho u_t)}$$

Where y^+ is dimensionless value of wall distance and u_t is the wall friction velocity.

Different domain sizes have tried for 2D simulation and findings are recoded. Some of the Domain are attached in this research paper. 2D geometries are prepared on ANSYS Design Modeler for different cases shown in *Figs. 2 to 4* and 3D geometry is prepared on ANSYS spaceclaim tool shown in *Fig. 9* and *10*. For 3D Geometry the distance of inlet, outlet, sides and top and bottom boundaries are 5D, 10D, 2D and 2D respectively. For 2D case meshing method used All triangle Method shown in *Figs. 5 to 8* but for 3D case meshing method is patch conforming method shown in *Figs. 11 to 13*.

Figure 2 2D Geometry of Domain size change of middle trial

Figure 3 2D Geometry of Domain size change of first trial

Figure 4 2D Geometry of Domain size change of last trial

Figure 5 Meshing of Domain size change of middle trial

Figure 6 Refinement around airfoil with inflation (from first boundary layer thickness) for middle trial

Figure 7 Meshing of Domain size change of last trial

Figure 8 Refinement around airfoil with inflation (from first trial)

Figure 9 3D geometry of VAWT in ANSYS Spaceclaim

Figure 10 3D view of Airfoils inside middle domain

Figure 11 Meshing of 3D Computational domain

Figure 12 Wireframe view of Airfoils inside Middle domain

Figure 13 Refinement mesh with inflation of Airfoils

Turbulence Model for Simulation

The turbulence model used in simulation is SST $k-\omega$ model. For the simulation $TSR=2.5$ and moment coefficient is assumed to be 0.1 for airfoil curves. To verify the accuracy of 2D and 3D simulation data of the 3.5Kw VAWT were compared with the McMaster University wind tunnel experimental data [1]. The numerical simulation has a positive direction along the X-axis and a wind speed of 10 m/s for the velocity inlet condition. The pressure outlet condition's gauge pressure is 0 Pa. The windmill turns in a anticlockwise direction. The comparable rotational angular velocity of the wind turbine is 20 rad/s when its TSR is 2.5. Convergence of residuals are set to 1×10^{-6} . The pressure-velocity coupling method of SIMPLE and the 2D and 3D unstable incompressible equation are employed for the 2D and 3D numerical simulation model used in this work. Among the available turbulence models, the SST $k-\omega$ model is chosen because it is more accurate in capturing the features of the flow field [1].

The main governing transport equations of $k-\omega$ SST model are as follows [10]:

$$\frac{\partial(\rho k)}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial(\rho u_i k)}{\partial x_i} = \frac{\partial}{\partial x_j} \left[\Gamma_k \frac{\partial k}{\partial x_j} \right] + \tilde{G}_k - Y_k + S_k \quad \text{-----(1)}$$

$$\frac{\partial(\rho \omega)}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial(\rho u_i \omega)}{\partial x_i} = \frac{\partial}{\partial x_j} \left[\Gamma_\omega \frac{\partial \omega}{\partial x_j} \right] + G_\omega - Y_\omega + D_\omega + S_\omega \quad \text{-----(2)}$$

$$\Gamma_k = \mu + \frac{\mu_t}{\sigma_k} \quad \text{-----(3)}$$

$$\Gamma_\omega = \mu + \frac{\mu_t}{\sigma_\omega} \quad \text{-----(4)}$$

$$\mu_t = \frac{\rho k}{\omega} \times \frac{1}{\max \left[\frac{1}{a^* a_1 \omega} \right]} \quad \text{-----(5)}$$

$$\sigma_k = \frac{1}{F_1 \sigma_{k,1} + (1-F_1) \sigma_{k,2}} \quad \text{-----(6)}$$

$$\sigma_{\omega} = \frac{1}{F_1\sigma_{\omega,1} + (1-F_1)\sigma_{\omega,2}} \quad \text{-----(7)}$$

$$Y_k = \rho\beta\omega^2 \quad \text{-----(8)}$$

$$\beta_i = F_1\beta_{i,1} + (1 - F_1)\beta_{i,2} \quad \text{-----(9)}$$

Where F_1 and F_2 are blended functions.

Model constants $\sigma_{k,1} = 1.176, \sigma_{\omega,1} = 2.0, \sigma_{k,2} = 1.0, \sigma_{\omega,2} = 1.168, a_1 = 0.31, \beta_{i,1} = 0.075$ and $\beta_{i,2} = 0.0828$.

Results and Discussions

Power Calculation

For Tips speed ratio (TSR=2.5)

Angular speed (ω) = $\frac{TSR \times V_i}{R}$

R=1.25m, $V_i=10$ m/s

Theoretical Power Calculation

For 2D Case

$$P_{\text{theoretical}} = \frac{1}{2} \rho A_s V^3 \text{ (Assumed thickness = 1m)}$$

$$= 0.5 \times 1.225 \times 2.5 \times 10^3$$

$$= 1531.25 \text{ Watt}$$

Actual Power Calculation from CFD

Case 1 (First trial of domain size change in simulation work)

This is first trial case of domain size assumption of simulation work. In which inlet distance from center is 1D shown in Fig. 3. Time steps for unsteady/ transient simulation is calculated from below formulas:

Circumference = $\Pi D = 3.14 \times 2.5 = 7.85$ m

Time to complete one revolution $t = \frac{\text{Distance covered in one revolution (circumference)}}{\text{Tangential Velocity}}$ which comes 0.314 seconds if it is divided by 360, dt will come 0.0008722 seconds which is used for simulation work. Torque Vs time steps graph is shown in Fig. 14 for this case.

Figure 14 Torque Vs Time steps 1st trial of domain size simulation

Actual Power (P_{actual}) = Average torque for 360° or One cycle (last 360-time steps) $\times \omega$

Which comes 846.6233255 Watts

Coefficient of Power (C_p) = $P_{\text{actual}}/P_{\text{air}} = 0.55$ and C_p experimental is **0.32** [1]. There is huge variation of results for this domain. Hence In research work, more domain sizes have been tried to get precise results.

Case 2 (middle iteration of domain size change in simulation work)

This is mid trial case of domain size assumption of simulation work. In which inlet distance from center is 5D shown in Fig. 2. In this case Actual power comes **520.882 watts** and C_p comes **0.34**. Which is very near to experimental $C_p = 0.32$ [1]. percentage error is **6.25%**. Torque Vs time steps graph is shown in Fig. 15 for this case.

Case 3 (last trial of domain size change in simulation work)

This is last trial case of domain size assumption of simulation work of this research paper. In which inlet distance from center is 7.5D shown in Fig. 4. In this case Actual power comes **504.112 watts** and C_p comes **0.33**. Which is very near to experimental $C_p = 0.32$ [1]. Percentage error is **3.125%**. Torque Vs time steps graph is shown in Fig. 16 for this case.

Figure 15 Torque Vs Time steps for mid trial of domain size change of simulation work

Figure 16 Torque Vs Time steps for last iteration of domain size change of simulation work

Case 4 (3D Geometry)

3D geometry shown in Fig. 9 is simulated on ANSYS Fluent with same turbulence model. 3D geometry simulation is still under process. Results obtained till now from 3D simulation are presented here. As 3D geometry has very large no. of nodes in meshing, its need more computational power. Torque Vs time steps graph is shown in Fig. 17 for this case.

Figure 17 3D geometry Torque vs Time steps

It is taking large time to produce/Converge the results. In this case Actual power comes **373.634 watts** (Due to the limitation of computational capability, more refined mesh could not be adopted which might further improve the computational results).

Visualization of results

All the post-processing of results is done on ANSYS CFD post. In this section Pressure contours and velocity streamlines are presented. Pressure contours around airfoils in 2D simulation for different cases are presented below from Figs. 18 to 21. Velocity streamlines for 2D simulations are shown in Fig. 22 to 23.

Figure 18 Pressure contour of turbineblades for middle trial case of domain size

Figure 19 Zoom view of Pressure contour of turbineblades for middle trial case of domain size

Figure 20 Pressure contour of turbine blades for last trial case of domain size

Figure 21 Zoom view of Pressure contour of turbine blades for last trial case of domain size

Figure 22 Velocity streamlines of turbine blades for middle trial case of domain size

Figure 23 Velocity streamlines of turbine blades for last trial case of domain size

Figure 24 Pressure Contours on single turbine blade 3D

Figure 25 Velocity streamlines of 3D turbine blades

Conclusions

Using 2D and 3D URANS CFD simulations, the current work examined the impact of domain size variation on VAWT performance at a tip speed ratio of 2.5.

Major derived conclusions are as follows:

1. The performance will be greatly overestimated if the result is sampled before the turbine has completed 15 to 20 revolutions. Then, following a few more revolutions, the solution is convergent and the results are becoming stable.
2. It has been shown that the minimum distance of 5D between the turbine center and the inlet will minimize the impact of the domain inlet on the turbine's performance. This results in a percentage error in C_p of 6.25%, which is within the allowable limit. The flow in this domain is velocity streamlined by a turbine with a proper blocking effect.
3. A smaller distance causes the C_p to be overestimated. C_p was measured as 0.55 for the first domain change trial when the inlet distance from the turbine center was 1D, which is 71.87% greater than the experimental value of C_p , which was 0.32.
4. The influence of domain outlet on wind turbine is determined to be minimized when there is a minimum distance between the turbine center and the outlet of 10D (the middle trial of the domain change in this research paper). It is discovered that this distance roughly corresponds to the turbine wake length. Because the turbine wake breaks off where it is not fully developed, shorter distances will cause the turbine's C_p to be underestimated.
5. Greater distances (12.5D from center to outlet) won't affect the C_p result in an undesired way because they provide a fully developed wake region. The value of C_p in this particular case is 0.33, and the measurement error

percentage is 3.125%. However, in this instance, it has been noted that there is not much significant change of C_p from middle trial but number of cells in mesh increased significant that need more computational power. Therefore, Middle trial domain size considered optimal for simulation in 2-Dimensional study.

6. For optimal results, the minimum domain distance (5D) between each side boundary and the turbine center is observed. Larger sizes lessen the turbine's blocking impact of turbine blades.

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